

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPING NEW LUBRICATING COMPOSITIONS FOR POWERED MARINE DIESELES

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Abstract

The widespread use of M-20B₂f motor oil used in ship makes the development of this modern analogue important and urgent. For this purpose, calcium salts of condensation products of alkylphenols with high alkaline number with formaldehyde and various amines, based on the replacement of detergent-dispersant VNII NP-360 and -354 additives used in the lubricating composition of the said oils were studied. By studying the detergent-dispersant and at the same time anti-oxidation properties of alkylphenolate additives at different temperatures and times, based on the amount of sediment formed during the oxidation process, low molecular volatile acids and acid number results, the use of AKI-114 and AKI-150 additives was preferred as high-performance detergent-dispersant additives in lubricating compositions of and M-20B₂f motor oils.

Keywords: motor oil, additive, ship and drilling equipment, alkylphenol, detergent-dispersing property, oxidation, alkaline number.

1. INTRODUCTION

The history of modern lubricating oils dates back to the beginning of oil drilling in Penselvania USA in the 19th century. At that time, whale oil was used as a lubricant for spinning and weaving machines, and it was then discovered that if mixed with oil, it was possible to extend the life of the machine by more than 10 years. Since then, petroleum-based lubricants have replaced fatty oils.

In the era of mass production of the 20th century, more complex mechanisms became in demande. Specially after the I, II world wars, cars, airplanes, diesel trains began to develop at a rapid pace, rockets, large ships, which led to the progress of essential oils and lubricants. In the 1920s, a method for refining oil with selective solvents was invented, and in the 1930s, the use of additives to improve the performance of lubricants began to spread in industry.

In the 1950s, when the jet liner was introduced, it became necessary to develop lubricating oils that perform well even in temperatures below 50 degrees below zero, leading to the development of Synthetic and Multi-Purpose oils. Hydrocracking was developed in the 1970s and the more advanced Hydroisomerization in the 1990s has allowed the development and production of a wide range of high quality mineral oil lubricants that can fully compete with synthetic oil.

Currently, much attention is paid not only to the performance characteristics of lubricants, but also to the factors of their impact on the environment, therefore many chemists, scientists, engineers, oil refining workers, metallurgists and other representatives of related

industries carry out research activities to improve the characteristics of lubricants.

Lubricating oils perform the following functions:

1. Reducing friction of the contacting parts,
2. Cooling of surfaces of rubbing parts.
3. Load balancing - lubricants form an oil film and accelerate the load
4. Cleaning - Prolonged use of the system can lead to corrosion or wear on the machinery, resulting in the appearance of contaminants. Engine oils, due to their detergent properties, allow you to clean the system from contaminina.
5. Sealing - Especially in a hydraulic system, lubricating oils serve to prevent leakage by creating a hydraulic film.
6. Prevention of corrosion - With prolonged contact of metal with water and oxygen, corrosion is formed. However, by covering the surface with a lubricating film, it is possible to prevent corrosion and extend the life of the system. (<http://www.s-oil7.com/rus/knowledge/basic/function.jsp>)

Currently, the leading companies in the field of production and consumption of lubricants in the world market are:

- Shell (UK - Netherlands)
- Exxon Mobil (USA)
- British Petroleum (UK - USA)
- Chevron (USA)
- Total (France)
- Petro Cina (China)
- OAO Lukoil (Russia)
- Sinopec (China)

- Valvolinc (USA)

It is known that lubricants used in various fields of technology mainly consist of 2 components: base oil and additive composition. Depending on the area of application of lubricating oils, the main quality indicators required for their operation include anti-oxidation, anti-corrosion, anti-corrosion, as well as detergent-dispersant, detergent, lubricant, etc. provides additives. Additives are organic compounds containing different functional groups and active elements. The questionnaire for additives in motor and transmission oils was compiled in 1985 in the "For Service Use" catalog. The questionnaire contains all the information on the chemical composition, physicochemical parameters, production technology of various functional additives in lubricants produced on a large scale from that year to recent years. [1, 2].

The main special requirements for each specific equipment are reflected in the normative documents (GOST) for their production and consumption: kinematic viscosity, viscosity index, alkali number, resistance to oxidation, corrosion resistance, lubricating properties, etc., which characterize the operational properties.

External equivalents of M-20B2 and M-20B2f engine oils for ship diesels are Shell (Rotella-50, Rimula R2-50), Mobile (Delvac 1150), BP (Energol HD 50), Exxon (Essolube HD 50), Castrol (Deusol CRH). 50) and so on. APIs are manufactured by companies according to the SD / SB SAE 50 classification. [3].

Additive - for fuel, lubricants, etc. are organic organic compounds that are added in small amounts and improve their performance properties.

Types of additives:

- Viscosity additives;
- depressant additives;
- against eating;
- detergent;
- against oxidation;
- dispersant;
- detergent-dispersant;
- anti-corrosion;
- anti-foaming;
- restorative; and so on.

Most additives are multifunctional. The total amount of additives in commercial oils is 15-20%. Additives containing depressants and viscosity additives are used to facilitate the transport, storage and dissolution of additives in base oils [4,5].

It is important that all motor oils contain multifunctional detergent-dispersant additives used as additives [6].

The purpose of the article is to replace some important detergent-dispersant additives with new modifications, to create a basis for the production of oils used in ship diesels in recent years using local raw materials with a number of imported additive packages [7].

The AKI-114 and AKI-150 detergent-dispersant additives used in the article are formaldehyde of alkylphenols and calcium salts of ammonia and amino acetic acid condensation products. ICA) -101 are new modifications [8, 9]. Here "AKI" represents the name of the Institute of Chemistry of Additives, the only academic institute in the field of additive chemistry in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Institute of Chemistry of Additives - (Russian "IHP" Institute of Chemistry Prisdok, eng. "ICA" Institute of Chemistry of Additives).

At present, research on the creation of new analogues of lubricants used in all machines and mechanisms in the country requires the provision of indicators in accordance with the normative document of oil - GOST. In these studies, as well as new modifications of withdrawn additives research is also very relevant. Therefore, our goal is to create new lubricant compositions of imported M-20B2f motor oils for ship diesels on the basis of local raw materials.

M-20B₂f (<https://cnrgoil.ru/sudovoe-maslo/m20v2f.html>) motor oil for diesel engines used in ship belong to group B₂ of motor oils used in different types of all-purpose diesel engines.

The main purpose of developing lubricating compositions of both oils, which belong to the high-oil groups, is the study of newly synthesized additives with highly effective functional properties and the correct selection of base oils. Ensuring the indicators characterizing the important physicochemical and operational properties of the analogues of the oils to be developed is their compliance with their external analogues (Mobilgard 412, Energol IC-MB 40, Energol DS3-104, Energol DL-MP 40).

Materials and method. Research on the development of M-20B₂f motor oil for ship diesels (<http://www.msc-mayak.ru/shop/show-product/228/1/dizel-chn18-22-6chnsp-18-22-8chspn-18-22/>) is related to the research of the compatibility of additives in the composition of the additive separately, with each other and with the base oil.

Figure 1 The ship diesel.

The additive composition of M-20B2f motor commodity oil (country of origin, Russian Federation) produced for ship diesels is given in 2 compositions.

First composition. Types of primary use of these oils consist of VNIINP-360 – 4%; PMS«A» – 3,3% or C-150 - 1,8% (C-300 -1,5%); AzNII-SIATIM-1 – 1,5%; PMS-200A – 0,003% additives with a mixture of MC-20 base oil and residual components.

Second composition. In other compositions, VNIINP-354 or 1,2% Df-11, 1,0-1,5% AzNII-SIATIM-1 or AFK, 0,003% PMS-200A are used.

For the development of new lubricating compositions of oils M-20B2 and M-20B2f, highly alkaline additives of the alkylphenolate type AKI-114 and AKI-150, which are new modifications of the additive IHP-101, which have been used for a long time in a number of oils, were taken as detergent-dispersing additives [10].

AKI-114 additive — is the calcium salt of the product of the condensation of alkylphenol with formaldehyde and ammonia. Alkaline number is 80.0 mgKOH/ g.

AKI-150 additive – is the calcium salt of the product of condensation of alkylphenol with methylen-bis formaldehyde amino acetic acid. Alkaline number is 150 mgKOH/ g.

where R=C₈-C₁₂.

The high alkaline number of AKI-114 and AKI-150 additives recommended for application compared to ICA-101 additive (alkaline number 50-55 mgKOH/g) in some cases leads to the provision of other functional properties of oils.

Results and discussion.

The choice of AKI series additives in APSM-1M (Figure 2) equipment is based on the determination of their properties of resistance to oxidation at different temperatures (120°C-140°C) and duration (30-40

hours) and optimum concentrations, and the amount of sediment, determination of the acid number, the amount of volatile low-molecular acids.

In the APSM-1M apparatus, oils are oxidized in VTI devices under the influence of oxygen of technical GOST 5583 in the presence of a catalyst at elevated temperatures with a metered flow rate of 50 ml / min and 200 ml / min. The error of maintaining the stability of oxygen consumption is not more than $\pm 10\%$. [GOST 981].

Figure 2. APSM-1 apparatus.

Lubricating compositions of M-20B2f oil (with additives AKI-150, C-400, Mixoil-3103, Viscoplex-5-309, PMS-200A in accordance with GOST 12337) and M-20B2 oils (with additives AKI-114, C-400, Mixoil-3103, Viscoplex-5-309, PMS-200A according to GOST 23497) were prepared on the basis of MS-20 (Russia) base oil. Here, AKI-114 and AKI-150 are highly alkaline multifunctional additives (synthesized

at the Institute of Chemistry of Additives NASA), Mix-oil 3103 – antioxidant and anticorrosive additive, C-400 - detergent-dispersant additive, Viscoplex -5-309 – depressoator, PMS-200A – anti-foam additive.

Anti-oxidation tests of alkylphenolate additives of different compositions have been carried out in APSM-1M equipment for 30 hours at 120°C, 30 and 40 hours at 140°C, 30 hours at 200 °C [11, 12]. Table 1.

Table 1.

Test results of resistance of AKI series additives to oxidation during different hours at 120°C

Composi-tions with additives	120°C 30 hours			120°C 40 hours		Amount of vola-tile low-molecu-lar acids, mg KOH/g
	Amount of the sedi-ment, %	Acid num-ber, mg KOH/g	Amount of vola-tile low-molecu-lar acids, mg KOH/g	Amount of the sedi-ment, %	Acid num-ber, mg KOH/g	
AKI-114	0,0731	0, 287	0,0068	0,0705	0,354	0,0070
AKI-150 (c)	0,0725	0, 176	0,0072	0,0700	0,257	0,0073

The results obtained in tests conducted at temperatures of 120°C, 140°C show the effect on the course of the process of resistance to oxidation, which depends on the composition and structure of detergent-dispersant additives, the alkaline number of additives, the location of the nitrogen atom in amino compounds.

The determination of the acid number indicates that the units of carbonated additives obtained during the test were 0,354 mgKOH/g.

By determining the amount of low-molecular volatile acids, it was determined that in all cases, regardless of the temperature of 140-200°C and the duration of 30, 40 hours, its amount differs very little. Table 2.

The results of the tests carried out showed that AKI-114 and AKI-150 series additives can be applied

at the same level as commodity additives in high-quality compositions in the development of motor oils for various purposes.

Table 2.

Indicators of AKI series additives for 40 hours at 140°C, for 30 hours at 200°C

Compositions with additives	140°C, 40 hours			200°C, 30 hours		Amount of low-molecular volatile acids, mgKOH/g
	Amount of the sediment, %	Acid number, mg KOH/q	Amount of low-molecular volatile acids, mgKOH/g	Amount of the sediment, %	Acid number, mg KOH/q	
AKI-114	0,0740	0,3870	0,0050	0,0745	0,3540	0,0070
AKI-150 (c)	0,0732	0,2600	0,0065	0,0741	0,2870	0,0090

Long-term tests of AKI series additives at higher temperatures did not yield positive results.

Lubricating compositions of experimental oil samples of optimal composition of M- 20B₂f lubricating composition with AKI-114, Mixoil-3103, C-400,

PMS-200A additives and M- 20B₂ lubricating composition with AKI-150, Mixoil-3103, C-400, PMS-200A additives were developed [13,14]. Table 3.

Laboratory tests of all physical and chemical properties were carried out by international ASTM methods.

Table 3.

Comparative results of physicochemical and operational properties of lubricating compositions

Indicators	M- 20B ₂ motor oil GOST 23497	MC-20 base oil AKI-114 Mixoil-3103 C-400 PIMC-200A	M- 20B ₂ f motor oil GOST 12337	MC-20 base oil AKI-150 Mixoil-3103 C-400 PIMC-200A	Test method
Kinematic viscosity, mm ² /s 100°C	18,0-22,0	20,12	19,0-22,0	21,02	ASTM D 445
Viscosity index	90	85	90	95	ASTM D 2270
Alkaline number, mgKOH / q, not to be less	3,5	3,5	2,8	3,6	ASTM D 4739
Sulphate ash,%, not to be more	1,3	0,79	0,65	0,38	ASTM D 874
Ignition temperature, set in open crucible, °C, not to be lower	235	270	230	275	ASTM D 92
Freezing temperature, °C, not to be higher	Minus 15	Minus 15	Minus 15	Minus 15	ASTM D 97
On C1 and C2 branded lead boards according to corrosivity GOST 377877, g/m ² , not to be more	No	No	10	No	GOST 20502
Resistance based on non-sedimentation induction period, 50 hours	Resists	Resists	Resists	Resists	GOST 11063
Colour, in IJHT calorimeter, the unit of IJHT (diluted 15:85) not to be more	7,5	8,0	3,5	3,0	ASTM D 1500
Density, 20°C, kg/m ³ , not to be more	900	898	900	895	ASTM D 4052
Washing potential, 250°C, %	Not normalized	90	Not normalized	95	QOST 10734

The performance of lubricant compositions with the use of high alkalinity additives AKI-114 and AKI-150, such as sulfate ash, flash point, washing potential, is considered to be superior to that of commercial oil. In particular, the content of sulfate ash for M-20B₂ motor oil is 0.79% against 1.3%, for M-20B₂f motor oil is 0.68% against 0.38%, the ignition temperature is 270°C against 235°C. The washing potential is 90 and 95% at 250° [15,16].

3. Conclusion.

The results of the tests carried out showed that AKI-114 and AKI-150 series additives can be applied at the same level as commodity additives in high-quality compositions in the development of motor oils for various purposes. [17]

The newly synthesized high-alkali AKI-114 and AKI-150 additives used in M-20B₂ and M-20B₂f motor oils used in ship diesels have been approved for their

high antioxidant and detergent-dispersing properties, and are recommended for qualification testing in lubricant compositions.

Thus, the new lubricating compositions of the newly developed M- 20B₂f motor oil fully meet the requirements set for motor oils used in modern ship diesels for their basic physicochemical and operational parameters and are recommended for application.

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